

DOI :

Evolution of Modern Diasporas and Diaspora Governance at State Level: Indian Experiences

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ABSTRACT

Human history is full of the stories of migration. There have been various waves of such migration and settlement with different pull and push factors. However, evolution of Modern Diasporas is closely linked with the movement of people in the colonial period. Ever growing advancements in transportation and communication technologies are giving further boost to international migration. It has resulted in the advent of Diaspora Governance at global, regional and state level. About two-third state of contemporary global system have evolved some kind of mechanism for Diaspora Governance. India holds distinction of having world's second largest Diaspora population, but it was initially reluctant to engage herself in their matters. However, India quickly recognized their importance and infrastructure of Diaspora Governance gradually developed. While Prime Minister Atal Bihari Vajpayee introduced active phase of Diaspora Governance in India, it has reached at the doorstep of our overseas population under the leadership of current Prime Minister Shri Narendra Modi.

Keywords : *Diaspora Governance, Slavery, Indentureship, Privileged Settlers, Free Passages.*

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT :

This research article is product of ICSSR funded project (under IMPRESS Scheme) on 'Migrant and Diasporic Communities in the Agenda of Global Governance: Opportunities and Challenges for India'. Author is highly indebted to the ICSSR for providing financial support to carry out research project.

INTRODUCTION

Movement of people from one place to another place is a fundamental characteristic of living beings. Anthropology believes that prior to the beginning of civilization, human beings passed through the stage of nomadism. History is evident that people have been crossing political boundaries- voluntarily or forcefully. Rubenstein explains rationales of migration by his theory of "push factor and pull factor". According to this theory, people decide to migrate because of push and pull

factors. A push factor induces people to move out of their present location, whereas a pull factor induces people to move into a new location. As migration for most people is a major step not taken lightly, both push

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Received	Reviewed	Accepted	Published
02-Feb.-2024	27-Mar.-2024	22-Apr.-2024	10-Jun.-2024

Volume	Issue	June	ISSN
No. 6	No. 1	2024	2583-1852(P), 2584-0878(O)

How to Cite this Article: Rajneesh Kumar. Evolution of ModernDiasporas and Diaspora Governance at State Level: Indian Experiences. *THE THIRD VOICE REALITY AND VISION*. 2024. Vol No-6. Issue No-1. June. Pp: 29-38. DOI

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DOI:

Article No - TVRV00054

and pull factors typically play a role. To migrate, people view their current place of residence so negatively that they feel pushed away, and another place so attractive that they feel pulled towards it. He identifies three major kinds of push and pull factors- economic, cultural and environmental (2002). Everett S. Lee defines migration as a permanent or semi-permanent change of residence, regardless of distance- short or long; nature- voluntary or involuntary; without making any distinction between external and internal relocation. He identifies four factors of migration- 1. Factors associated with the area of origin; 2. Factors associated with the area of destination; 3. Intervening obstacles; and 4. Personal factors (1966). Since the beginning of the practice of colonialism a new era of migration and settlement began whereas in most of the cases people were able to retain certain features in the new land of destiny brought from homeland. Evolution of modern Diasporas is indeed attributed to this cruel part of history. Nevertheless, practice of migration has accelerated many folds in the post-colonial era and huge influx of migration has necessitated emergence of institutional mechanism to deal with such communities at the state and global level. This article intends to study evolution of modern Diasporas and Diaspora Governance at State level with adequate focus on Indian experiences. It is divided into four parts- forms of migration in colonial period and evolution of Modern Diasporas, current trends in international migration, institutional mechanism of Diaspora Governance at State Level and Indian way of Diaspora Governance.

Migration in Colonial Period and Evolution of Modern Diasporas

The history of migration and evolution of contemporary Diasporic communities could be traced from the European exploration of so-called new parts of the world and beginning of the practice of colonialism. There were many waves of migration between fifteen to twentieth centuries in the period of colonialism and imperialism. Broadly speaking such migration occurred under four categories- slavery, indentureship, free passages, and privileged settlers.

Slavery : In the literary sense- a slave is a man considered property of other man. Dictionary meaning of slave is ‘the condition of being enslaved, held, or owned as human chattel or property; bondage’ (dictionary.com). Thus, slavery is ‘a practice or institution that treats or recognizes some human beings as the legal property of others.’ Britannica defines slavery as a

“condition in which one human being was owned by another. A slave was considered by law as property, or chattel, and was deprived of most of the rights ordinarily held by free persons” (britannica.com).

Slavery has been in practice in Europe and other parts of the world since ancient times. However, it became a means to mass exodus of humans in the colonial period with the prevalence of the system of slave trade. According to Steven Mintz, from 1526 to 1867 approximately 12.5 million people from Africa were transported to America and Europe. He writes:

“The number of people carried off from Africa reached 30,000 per year in the 1690s and 85,000 per year a century later. More than eight out of ten Africans forced into the slave trade crossed the Atlantic between 1700 and 1850. The decade 1821 to 1830 saw more than 80,000 people a year leaving Africa in slave ships. Well over a million more—one-tenth of those carried off in the slave trade era followed within the next twenty years”(Mintz, n.d.).

Indentureship : Practice of slavery came under severe criticism since late eighteenth century consequently it was abolished by governmental regulations in Europe in the first half of nineteenth century. Repatriation of people as slave was banned in the British Empire by the Act of Emancipation of 1834. Similarly, it was abolished in French colonies in 1846, and in 1873 in the Dutch colonies. However, it led to severe shortage of workers in the sugar, coffee, tea, cocoa, rice and rubber plantations in the colonies (Kadekar, 2005). Thus, colonial powers devised a new means of transportation of people- indentureship. Technically, the system of indentureship was a method to recruit workers on contractual basis under which people from India, China and other countries were recruited with an agreement to work in colonial countries for the stated period on specified terms and conditions. However, on the grounds such agreements were done through recruitment agents and with people not able to read and understand the prescribed terms and conditions. Those were just giving their thumb impression on the paper without knowing the consequences of it. Recruitment agents made false promises and workers were often not aware of the places they are going to work. Once the agreement was signed these workers were becoming bonded labours having no choice to withdraw from so called contract. It refers to the “transfer of labour power from metropolises to colonies” or as a “system of bonded labour with a resemblance to slavery” (Harris, 2010: 147). The system

of indentureship was as cruel as slavery, Tinker provides detail account of similarities in the both the systems and concludes that it was a 'New form of Slavery' (1974).

The system of slave trade was responsible for the displacement of millions of people from Africa. Contrary to this indenture system was largely prevalent in Asia especially in China and India. First it was introduced in China. Loss occurred in two Opium Wars forced Qing Dynasty of China to provide land rights to European powers. Qing Dynasty opened five treaty ports- Guangzhou, Xiamen, Fuzhou, Ningpo and Shanghai- for free trade and colonial merchants obtained privileges to acquire labourers from China. This was the time when people of China were facing extremely difficult living conditions clubbed with many natural calamities. This prompted recruitment of Chinese labourers to transport other parts of the world and number of coolie agency came into existence for this purpose working through *ketou* to overcome linguistic barriers. Between mid-1840s and 1870s in almost three-decade period, 44 major coolie agencies existed and majority of them were British owned, some of them were controlled by French, Spanish, German, American and Portuguese. Notably six of them were owned by Chinese. These coolie agencies transported Chinese labourers to West Indies, British Guiana, Cuba and Peru, Australia, Singapore and Sumatra (Ching-hwang, 2013). The British colonists were impressed by the example of Latin American and Cuban colonists who had imported Chinese labourers from Macao, a Portuguese settlement, to work on their plantations (Campbell 1969). Thus, the indenture system was introduced in India as well which was continued till first two decades of twentieth century.

Free passages : Colonial subjugation also propelled migration of people from colonies to the European countries which was voluntary in nature as many people went there to pursue higher education, trading, administrative works and so on as temporary settlers and many of them decided to make permanent settlement in these countries. Although, they were treated as second class citizens and faced discriminations but found better life prospects and decided to make their land of destiny to these countries. Nevertheless, centuries old trade related migration to various countries continued throughout the colonial period. While millions of people from India and China were transported through system of indenture many others were sent by the colonial masters as government servants in the capacities of administrative staff, clerks, supervisors and other support service providers. Such people were referred as

'imperial auxiliaries' (Tinker, 1974). Further, many people migrated willingly to cater to the needs of indentured labourers. Those were barbers, tailors, washer-man, goldsmith, petty-shopkeepers etc. Business oriented people from India- 'Baniyas of United Provinces, Marwaris of Rajputana, Chettiars of Madras, Pathans of north-west, and Gujaratis of Bombay Presidency' utilized this opportunity to expand their trade in various countries (Kadekar, 2005).

Privileged settlers : The European exploration of so-called new world led by Italian navigator Christopher Columbus (1492) and Portuguese navigator Vasco da Gama (1498) was followed by the era of colonialism. For the next four centuries different European powers ventured in the parts of Asia, Africa, America, Caribbean, and Pacific initially for trade and later established themselves as ruler in many places. All the powerful nation-states of Europe sent their people to further their imperial plans in various parts of the world. The Spanish, Portuguese, Dutch, German, French and British colonists strategically established 'White Settlements' in many countries (Cohen, 2008). Currently, USA, Australia, New Zealand etc. have substantial population of the descendants of those settlers. In many other countries- South Africa, Kenya, Zimbabwe etc. there are still large number of such people. These people can be kept in the category of privileged settlers as those migrated willingly and enjoyed all luxuries during the colonial period and many of them are still influential in local societies of their residence.

Current Trends of International Migration : Although, the practice of colonialism began declining towards middle of the twentieth century and now almost each part of the world enjoys independence in terms of political rule; the trend of international migration is not only continued but also has been on rise over the decades. This is largely attributed to the advent of modern means of transportation and communication. The International Migration Report-2024 notes that today international migration is at an all-time high and about 281 million people are residing outside their country of birth. They constitute almost 3.6 per cent of the world population. It observes that "migration is not uniform across the world, but is shaped by economic, geographic, demographic and other factors, resulting in distinct migration patterns, such as migration "corridors" being developed over many years" (IOM, 2024, 3). Table-1 provides a detailed account of increasing trends of international migration from 1970 to 2020.

Table-1
International Migrants, 1970–2020

Year	Number of international migrants	Migrants as a % of the world's population
1970	8,44,60,125	2.3
1975	9,03,68,010	2.2
1980	101 983 149	2.3
1985	11,32,06,691	2.3
1990	15,29,86,157	2.9
1995	16,12,89,976	2.8
2000	17,32,30,585	2.8
2005	19,14,46,828	2.9
2010	22,09,83,187	3.2
2015	24,79,58 ,644	3.4
2020	28,05,98,105	3.6

Source: *World Migration Report-2022*, P. 23.

A scrutiny of the migration data reveals that the United States of America is the most popular destination for migrants and the country hosts more than 51 million people categorized as international migrants. With 16 million international migrants, Germany is the second most popular destination. Saudi Arabia hosts about 13 million international migrants and ranks third. The Russian Federation is home for 12 million international migrants and ranks fourth. With 9 million international migrants the United Kingdom is placed in the fifth position in terms of most popular destination countries for international migrants (IOM, 2021, 24).

In terms of proportion of international migrants in the total population, Oceania ranks first and it has 22 per cent of the population born in other countries. Northern America has the second largest share of international migrants at 15.9 per cent, followed by Europe at 11.6 per cent. Latin America and the Caribbean, Africa, and Asia have international migrant shares of 2.3, 1.9, and 1.8 per cent respectively (IOM, 2021, 24).

However, in terms of total stock of international migrants, Europe accounts first as it is home to 87 million migrants which constitutes about 30.9% of the total international migrant population. 86 million international migrants are hosted by Asia and those are 30.5% of the total population of international migrants. Northern America is the destination for 59 million international migrants which accounts for 20.9% of total international migrant's population. Africa is home to 25

million migrants which accounts 9% of total international migrants (IOM, 2021, 23). Further, World Migration Report notes that "Over the past 15 years, the number of international migrants in Latin America and the Caribbean has more than doubled from around 7 million to 15 million, making it the region with the highest growth rate of international migrants and the destination for 5.3 per cent of all international migrants. Around 9 million international migrants live in Oceania, or about 3.3 per cent of all migrants (IOM, 2021, 23).

In terms of migrant sending countries the World Migration Report places India in the top position and states that nearly 18 million people born in India are living abroad. Mexico is the second most significant origin country of international migrants and it sent about 11 million people to other countries. The Russian Federation is the third largest origin country, followed closely by China (around 10.8 million and 10 million respectively). The fifth most significant origin country is the Syrian Arab Republic, with over 8 million people living abroad (IOM, 2021, 25).

International migration has vital significance in global politics, economy, and culture. It is a matter of fact that whenever people migrate they carry with them a socio-cultural baggage which among other things consists of a predefined social identity, a set of religious belief and practices, a framework of norms and value governing family and kinship organizations, food habits, language and so on in their host-land. More important, the migrants are not inevitably irrevocably cut off completely from the land of their breed. With its intricate web of demographic, social, economic and political determinants and consequences, this is a topic that has moved to the forefront of national and international agenda as well as, has attracted considerable attention of academia in our age. There is an increasing trend among scholars to study socio-cultural aspects of migrant communities under the rubric of 'Diaspora'.

Diaspora Governance

Diasporic communities have attracted adequate attention of academicians, policy makers and bureaucrats due to their inherent capabilities of influencing home and host governments as well as bilateral and international relations. Traditionally, those have been studied under the concepts of 'public diplomacy', 'Diaspora diplomacy' or 'soft power'. However, those merely explains state-led initiatives ignoring crucial elements of other elements- family networks, community

organizations, religious grids and so on. Thus, contemporary scholars prefer to use the term ‘Diaspora Governance’. According to Alan Gamlen (2014: 21) “Diaspora governance is a multi-layered matter, involving not just national and international but also local institutions and processes”. Thus, mere inter-governmental arrangements are not sufficient to address issues of migrant and diasporic communities. Instead, effort should be made to avoid self-segregation of these communities and enhance process of intermingling with indigenous communities to attain better social coherence and integration with adequate opportunities of identity retention. Gamlen argues:

“the border-crossing nature of such activities is of increasing interest to an international community that is seeking ways to cooperate multilaterally over the management of international migration in the absence of a centralized global migration governance framework akin to the International Monetary Fund or World Trade Organization. Though aware of their interdependence over international migration, states see it as an issue over which they, and no international bureaucracy, should exercise sovereignty” (Gamlen, 2014: 21).

Institutional Mechanism of Diaspora Governance at State Level

With the growing importance of migrant and Diasporic communities, there has been phenomenal growth in Diaspora institutions in different nation-states. Although there have been Diaspora institutions since over a century, but their recent rise is unprecedented. Today, ‘Diaspora institutions are a regular feature of political life in many parts of the world; only a handful existed in 1980, but currently over half of United Nations Member States now have such institutions, and many are fully fledged government ministries’ (Gamlen, 2015). The rise of Diaspora institutions and their implications are explained by author as: “...These institutions matter because they connect recent developments in the global governance of migration, with current patterns of national and transnational sovereignty and citizenship, and new ways of constructing individual identity in relation to new collectivities. They have been overlooked partly because of this newness, but also partly because they operate in the grey zone between domestic politics and international relations – a zone that is growing more dynamic and significant in world politics” (Gamlen, 2015).

Figure-1

Percentage of United Nations Member States with diaspora institutions, by institution type, 1980-2014

Source: A. Gamlen, M.E. Cummings & P.M. Vaaler, “Explaining the rise of diaspora institutions”, *Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies*, Vol. 45, No. 4, 2019, P. 494.

Chris McIntyre, Elodie Jacoby and Alan Gamlen examined debates about the meaning, uses and the history of the word Diaspora in 130 member states of the United Nations and found in just over a third of the 130 states they studied used the actual word ‘Diaspora’, while a third used a different word to describe a similar population, and just under a third did not appear to discuss the topic much at all. So, among these 130 countries two third have evolved mechanism to deal with affairs of their people (citizens, erstwhile citizens and their descendants) living abroad (2014: 3). This study clearly indicates that the importance of the Diaspora has been recognized by the majority of the states in the world. The survey also provides insight on the institutional mechanism in homeland to deal with Diaspora. Generally, the affairs of such people are dealt with by Diaspora ministries, labour ministries, foreign ministries, executive offices, and other ministries. There are dedicated ministries to Diaspora with different names such as- Ministry of Malians Abroad in Mali, State Committee for Work with the Diaspora in Azerbaijan, Ministry of Haitians Living Abroad in Haiti, and Ministry of Emigrated Communities in Cape Verde. In many countries labour ministries are handling such matters- Ministry of Labour and Employment in Nepal,

Sri Lanka’s Ministry of Foreign Employment Promotion and Welfare, National Agency for External Labor Migration Abroad in Uzbekistan, Ministry of Expatriates’ Welfare and Overseas Employment in Bangladesh. In many countries such affairs are handled by executive authority itself- Office of the President in Sierra Leone, Moldova’s State Chancellery, the governments of Romania and Pakistan, and the Office of the President of Turkey. In some cases, such matters are dealt by various other ministries or a group of ministries like- Hungary’s Ministry of Public Administration and Justice, Namibia’s Ministry of Immigration and Home Affairs, and Russia’s Federal Migration Service. However, in the majority of the cases foreign ministries are officially assigned to handle the issues of their Diaspora (McIntyre, Jacoby and Gamlen: 2014, 19). It is noteworthy to mention that in India for about a decade there was the Ministry of Overseas Indian Affairs to look into the matters of Diaspora, later it was merged with Ministry of External Affairs in 2016. Nevertheless, in each case ministries work with various committees, advisory councils, other state institutions and governmental or non-governmental research organizations.

Table-2
Institutional Structure for Migrant and Diasporic Population in Homeland
 (In percentage of total 130 surveyed countries)

Term used	Responsible Ministry					No data
	Diaspora	Foreign Affairs	Labour	Executive	Other	
With use of terms diaspora	11.4	37.5	6.3	17.1	5.2	21.9
With use of other term	12.4	38.0	9.9	12.4	9.9	17.4
Including both (diaspora and other terms)	12.3	38.4	8.2	14.2	7.8	19.2

Source: C. McIntyre, E. Jacoby & A. Gamlen, *Working definitions of ‘diaspora’ used in migrants’ states of origin.* (Washington DC: World Bank, 2014). P. 19.

DIASPORA GOVERNANCE: INDIAN EXPERIENCES

India is one of the leading powers in terms of migration and Diasporic communities. Estimates on current strength of Indian communities living abroad varies from 25 million to 32 million, but it is an established fact that

it has the second largest Diaspora in the world that is only next to Chinese Diaspora. On the other hand, it hosts several migrant and diasporic communities. Many of them are integral part of India contributing to the growth story of the nation. Some of them are residing here as refugee and temporary migrants, many of them

reached here from neighbourhood due to ever going on religious persecution. At the same time, India is also facing acute crisis of illegal immigrants even since its independence. This has necessitated evolution of institutional mechanism as well as informal patterns of Diaspora Governance in India.

Over past seven and half decades, Diaspora Governance in India witnessed various ups and downs attributed to prevailing circumstances- domestic compulsions, situations in hostlands, international environment and personality of people involved in decision making process. Diaspora engagement policies of Indian government gradually evolved from the period of active disassociation in the first few decades after independence to the period of close alignment in the twenty-first century (Gupta, 2020). Independence of India brought two major challenges of Diaspora Governance- settlement of millions of people reaching from current Pakistan and Bangladesh made homeless due to their religious identities; and question of people went outside India to serve interests of colonial powers. Our leadership extended all possible support to victims of partition and kept door open for people residing outside India through Article-8 of our constitution. However, people of Indian origin holding citizenship of other countries were encouraged to identify themselves with their place of destiny. As, first Prime Minister of India, Pandit Jawaharlal Nehru said,

“It is the consistent policy of the Government that persons of Indian origin who have taken foreign nationality should identify themselves with and integrate in the mainstream of social and political life of the country of their domicile. The government remains naturally alive to their interests and general welfare and encourages cultural contacts with them. As far as Indian citizens residing abroad are concerned, they are the responsibility of the Government of India...” (cited in Gangopadhyay, 2005: 99).

Fresh influx of temporary migration since late 1960s largely attributed to ‘oil boom’, pressure from socio-cultural organizations and economic needs forced Indian government to rethink on the policy of active disassociation. Ms. Indira Gandhi termed them ‘cultural ambassador of India’ in 1981 during her visit to Fiji. To facilitate investment of overseas Indians in the country a special approval committee was constituted in 1986 in the Department of Industrial Development for speedy clearances of their industrial proposals. Further, an Indo-NRI Chamber of Commerce and Culture was set up in

1987 to promote the engagement of overseas Indians in the economy of India. To deal with vulnerable situation of Indian citizens going to work in West Asian countries, government introduced a policy of compulsory registration of recruitment agents of labourers to prevent the exploitation and deportation of the workforce going abroad (Dubey, 2011: 259). In a bid to unite overseas Indians living in different corners of the world with the identity of their motherland, the Global Organization of People of Indian Origin (GOPIO) was formed in 1989 with the active support of Indian government.

With the introduction of New Economic Policy of India in 1991 a new era of Liberalization, Privatization and Globalization (LPG) began in the country. It also coincided with the increasing thrust on proactive involvement of Diaspora in the economy of motherland as well as recognition of vast potentials of overseas Indians in the development process back in home. This was the period when Indian economy was passing through severe crisis- having lowest level of foreign exchange reserve, inflation, low credit rating made the situation whereas it was at the verge to collapse. After the nuclear test-II in 1998, to overcome the foreign exchange crises Government of India launched attractive financial schemes like Resurgent India Bonds and could secure US\$4.2 billion in a short span of time (Gupta, 2020: 90). It was a landmark contribution of Indian Diaspora to motherland. On 18 August 2000, Government of India constated a High-Level Committee on Indian Diaspora (HLCID) under the chairmanship of Dr. L.M. Singhvi. The Committee submitted its report on 19 December 2001 which was accepted by Indian Government marking the beginning of the active phase of Diaspora engagement.

The first Pravasi Bhartiya Divas was organized in January 2003 with 1,904 foreign delegates, including the Prime Minister of Mauritius, and 1,200 domestic delegates (Gupta, 2020: 90-91). On the question of granting dual citizenship to Indian Diaspora, Shri Atal Behari Vajpayee then Prime Minister of India stated:

“We are in favour of dual citizenship but not dual loyalty. The loyalty with India will remain but they will also be loyal to the country where they have taken citizenship but it has been resolved now. I am hopeful that Indians settled abroad will find it suitable” (Gangopadhyay, 2005: 111).

It was decided to convene the PBD every year on ‘9 January’ which has special significance for India as on

this day Mahatma Gandhi, the most eminent PravasiBharatiya, returned to India in 1915 from South Africa (Pradhan and Mohapatra, 2020: 154). Government of India also confers PBSA to notable PIO/NRI under different categories. Based on recommendations of the HLCID government introduced PIO Card scheme. The card provides visa-free access to India, with cardholders having many rights like NRIs except voting rights (Gupta, 2020: 91). In view of long and persistent demand for 'dual citizenship', particularly from the Indian Diaspora in North America and other developed countries, the Government of India initially considered it in the cases of PIOs living in 7 countries - US, UK, Canada, Australia, New Zealand, and Singapore (Gangopadhyay, 2005: 111-12). However, in 2006 it launched the Overseas Citizens of India (OCI) Card scheme which was open to all overseas Indians residing in the any part of the world. In subsequent years, both PIO card and OCI card were merged making a single scheme.

To look into the matters of Indian Diaspora, Government of India constituted a separate Ministry of Overseas Indian Affairs (MOIA) in 2004. In 2005, then President of India A.P.J. Abdul Kalam urged overseas Indian community to help the country in the period of crisis as well as rural development of India. Thus, he proposed the establishment of an Overseas Indian Research Foundation (OIRF) to support research in challenging areas including earthquake prediction, and establishment of 'Providing Urban Amenities in Rural Areas (PURAs) to involve themselves in extending urban amenities to rural areas of the country (Pradhan and Mohapatra, 2020: 155). To familiarizes Indian-origin youth with their Indian roots and contemporary India government has introduced the Know India Programme (KIP). Similarly, many editions of 'Know Goa Programme' (KGP) were organized for NRI/PIO youths whose forefathers were migrated from Goa and are presently residing in overseas. In view of promoting academic interaction between offspring of overseas Indians and higher education institutions of motherland, Indian government introduced the Scholarship Programme for Diaspora Children (SPDC) in 2006-07 (Gupta, 2020: 91).

However, the engagement of India with Indian Diaspora has been truly redefined in the current government referred as the Modi Doctrine. Current Prime Minister

of India Shri Narendra Modi considers Indian Diaspora – a 'living bridge' between India and countries of their residence. Modi coined this term during his London visit in 2015, which is now an essential component of the 2030 Roadmap for India-UK Future Relations. The idea of 'living bridge- 'summed up in two words, over two decades of Modi's consistent, committed and open engagement with probably India's most ardent constituency of natural ambassadors: global Indians' (Ladwa and Barai, 2022: 347). In the first visit to the USA after becoming Prime Minister of India, Modi addressed one of the largest gatherings in the Madison Square Garden, New York on 28 September 2014 with more than 20,000 people inside and many thousands waiting outside as those could not get chance to enter due to overcrowding. *The Washington Post* published this even on 28 September 2014 with headline- 'India's Modi was once denied US entry, Sunday, he was the star at Madison Square Garden' (Ladwa and Barai, 2022: 347). Subsequently, reaching to Diaspora and addressing gatherings of overseas Indians became a persistent feature of foreign visits of Prime Minister of India, Shri Narendra Modi and he established direct contacts with Diaspora in South Africa, UK, Germany, Australia and elsewhere. Shri S. Jaishankar, External Affairs Minister, Government of India writes,

"The evolution of our diaspora policy bears similar hallmarks of core beliefs and strong care. It is now widely accepted that the Madison Square Garden event on 28 September 2014 was a watershed in that domain. Prime Minister Modi had been invited to come to the US by President Obama during the congratulatory phone call. My first call on him thereafter as the Ambassador in the US naturally focused on a possible visit. The PM brought up the subject of the diaspora, which he described as a great strength of the nation. They needed to discover their own voice and we needed to consolidate their role as a bridge. The instructions for the MSG event flowed from this belief. It must be organized in a manner that its sound would reverberate not just in the US and India, but across the world. That it certainly did, for most part because the intensity of the PM's connect to the audience was so manifest. Thus began a unique experiment in popular diplomacy that has been envy of many other leaders and countries. Equally it has boosted the pride of the diaspora wherever he spoke" (2022: 373-374).

The way Prime Minister is reaching to overseas Indians has built confidence among overseas Indians that government is sincerely engaging them and those will

get support from motherland whenever it is required. The pro-active approach towards Diaspora is duly reflected in the tweet of late external affairs minister Smt. Sushma Swaraj in which she assured ‘Even if you are stuck on the Mars, Indian Embassy there will help you’ (Gupta, 2020: 91-92). The proactive approach of government towards Diaspora is also reflected in various operations carried out to rescue Indians in distress such as Operation Sankat Mochan in Sudan 2016, Operation Nistar in Yemen in 2018, Operation Devi Shakti in Afghanistan and the Vande Bharat Mission (VBM) that repatriated seven million Indians during the Covid-19 pandemic (Jaishankar, 2022: 373).

To intensify ties between Diaspora and India, current government has taken many new initiatives. In 2015, during the 13th PBD Prime Minister Shri Narendra Modi launched an online quiz competition- ‘Bharat Ko Jano’ for young overseas Indians residing outside India. The top 3 winners of the competition get medals by Hon’ble PM in the next PBD Convention. To attract best talents in the field of science and technology from Indian Diaspora and facilitate them to undertake collaborative research work in India government has introduced the Visiting Advanced Joint Research (VAJRA) scheme in 2017. To provide the PIOs an opportunity to reconnect with their Indian roots through a sponsored pilgrimage tour across India government has launched the Pravasi Teerth Darshan Yojana (PTDY) in 2018-19 for elderly generation of PIOs between the age group of 45-65 years from 07 Girmitiya countries- Fiji, Guyana, Mauritius, South Africa, Suriname, Trinidad & Tobago, Reunion Island Gupta, 2020: 91). Approach of current government towards Diaspora could be summed up in the words of Ladwa and Barai,

“If one looks closer at Modi’s approach in developing people-to-people connections, one starts to see a pattern emerging. He has, time and again, demonstrated his ability to capture the public mood, address public grievances, operationalize (often at scale) ideas and institutionalize these within the existing governance framework. Examples of these include how Indian embassies around the world are mandated to engage with diaspora organizations in a manner and depth never witnessed before- through regular outreach programmes, celebration of Indian festivals and important national days, and to actively seek inputs on governance and policy matters. Similarly, significant work has been done to streamline and make visa and OCI card processing as automated as possible, reducing arbitrary human intervention” (2022: 352-353).

CONCLUSION

Migration and settlement from one place to other is a permanent feature of human beings. Although evolution of state system brought certain restriction on it, but it has been continued throughout history. However, modern Diasporas are byproduct of the colonialism. During this period millions of people were taken from one part of the world to others. Some of them migrated as privileged settlers, some others voluntarily immigrants but majority of them went as ‘slave’ or ‘indenture workers’- victims of cruel practices of that period. Nevertheless, settlers were able to retain their socio-cultural identities and to some extent relations with their original habitations coming under the ambit of Diaspora. In the post-colonial world there has been various push and pull factors to accelerate international migration and today it is all time high. People living away from their country of citizenship constitutes about 3.6 percent of the global population. If we add the people having citizenship of countries of their current residence and possess traits of Diaspora this number may increase many folds. Thus, Diasporas have become indispensable part of governance at global, regional or state level. There has been phenomenal growth in global and regional mechanisms of Diaspora Governance. Majority of states have also evolved ways and means of Diaspora Governance at their own level. India with a huge Diasporic population have also developed substantial infrastructure to govern her Diaspora. Initially, Indian leadership was reluctant to show interests on matters of Diaspora. The constitution of the High Level Committee on Indian Diaspora during the period of Shri Atal Bihari Vajpayee marked active phase of Diaspora Governance and under the leadership of current Prime Minister Shri Narendra Modi it has reached at the doorstep of overseas Indians.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Not applicable

AUTHOR’S CONTRIBUTIONS

Author himself responsible for the first manuscript draft. Author has contributed to subsequent drafts and approved the final version.

FUNDING

No funding received for this study

AVAILABILITY OF DATA AND MATERIALS

No datasets were generated or analysed during the current study

Declarations

Ethics approval and consent to participate

Not applicable.

Consent for publication

Not applicable.

Competing interests

The author declares no competing interests.

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